

LANTHANIDE COMPLEXES DERIVED FROM TETRADENTATE MACROCYCLIC LIGAND: SYNTHESIS, CHARACTERIZATION AND ANTIMICROBIAL STUDIES

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ABSTRACT

Complexes of La(III), Ce(III), Nd(III), Sm(III) and Eu(III) were synthesized with triethylene tetraamine, 2,3-butanedione and metal salt in a 1:1:1 molar ratio results in the formation of a new series of tetraaza macrocyclic complexes: M[2,3-dimethyl-1,4,7,10-tetraaza cyclododeca-1,3-diene]. The ligand was obtained by the condensation of Triethylene tetraamine with 2,3-butanedione and characterized by elemental analysis, IR and ¹H NMR spectral studies. The Complexes were characterized by IR, ¹HNMR, UV-Vis spectral studies, conductivity and magnetic susceptibility measurements. The metal complexes were also tested for their *in vitro* antimicrobial activities against the growth of some fungal and bacterial species in order to assess their inhibiting potential.

Keywords : Tetraaza macrocycle, Antimicrobial activities, Template synthesis, Lanthanides

INTRODUCTION

Over couple of years the design and synthesis of complexes of lanthanide metal ions with macrocyclic ligands constitute a fascinating area of research because of their importance in basic and applied chemistry [1-3]. The synthetic, kinetic and structural aspects [4-5] of polyaza macrocyclic complexes have received considerable attention and a variety of such systems have been synthesized. A number of nitrogen donor macrocyclic derivatives have long been used in analytical, industrial, catalytic and medical applications [6-9]. The stability of macrocyclic complexes depends upon a number of factors, including the number and types of donor atoms present in the ligand and their relative positions within the macrocyclic skeleton, as well as the number and size of the chelate ring formed on complexation [10]. Macrocyclic ligands are able to recognize the presence of lanthanide metal ions. Therefore they are widely used in the selective extraction of metals [11] and as NMR shift reagents [12]. The design of macrocycles capable of forming stable lanthanide (III) complexes

not only would allow further study of the coordination properties of these metal ions but also would enable chemists to explore more fully certain important emerging properties of these complexes.

In view of these facts, reaction of the Lanthanoid metal ion and macrocyclic ligand has been carried out and structure of the resulting complexes were investigated using spectroscopic techniques. The complexes were characterized with the help of various physico-chemical techniques, such as elemental analyses, I-R, NMR and electronic spectral studies and magnetic susceptibility. These macrocyclic complexes were also screened for their *in vitro* antibacterial and antifungal activity.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

All the chemicals and solvents used in this study were of analytical grade.

Synthesis of complexes of [Me₂(12)dieneN₄]

All the reported macrocyclic complexes were prepared by the template method. Solution of triethylenetetraamine (1.50 ml; 0.01 mol) and 2,3-

butanedione (0.88 ml; 0.01 mol) in minimum quantity (20 ml) of dry and cold methanol were mixed and to this a methanolic solution of corresponding metal salt (0.01 mol) was added with constant stirring. The mixture was refluxed for 6h and than 1 ml concentrated hydrochloric acid or nitric acid according to salt was added. The mixture was further refluxed for

1h. The volume was than reduced to half on a steam bath and set aside for 30 minutes. The colored product formed was filtered off through a sintered crucible, washed with methanol and dried in *vacuo*.

***In vitro* antibacterial and antifungal assay**

Primary screening

The antimicrobial activities of the newly synthesized compounds were evaluated by the Serial dilution method against seven pathogenic and non-pathogenic bacterial strains i.e. Bacillus brevis MTCC 1952, Escherichia coli MTCC 1695, Klebsiella pneumonia MTCC 2405, Pseudomonas aeruginosa MTCC 2295, Staphylococcus aureus MTCC87, Staphylococcus epidermidis MTCC 435 and Salmonella typhimurium MTCC 98 and three fungal strains i.e. Aspergillus niger-ORS-4, Aspergillus flavus and Candida tropicalis. The bacterial cultures were maintained on the media prescribed by MTCC, IMT, Chandigarh by sub culturing them on a fresh slant after every 4-5 weeks and incubating them at the appropriate temperature for appropriate time and fungal strains were maintained on potato dextrose agar (2% dextrose, 2.5% agar in potato extract) slants, stored at 4°C and renewed every month. Stock solutions (10 mg/ml) for all the macrocyclic complexes were prepared in DMSO to determine the Minimal Inhibitory Concentration (MIC). DMSO was used as control for all the test compounds. Antimicrobial activities of the synthetic compounds were studied according to the method as described [13].

A series of tubes containing culture media, prepared by dissolving appropriate amounts of the media components in 100 ml of double distilled water were used. The final pH was adjusted with 1N NaOH and 1N HCl. The broth was sterilized at 121°C for 15 minutes. The media after sterilization was inoculated with 1% of the seeded culture and 5 ml of the inoculated culture media were dispensed into rimless ‘pyrex’ test tubes plugged with sterile non-absorbent cotton wool under aseptic condition. The various concentration of each of the variety of compounds were added. The tubes were incubated and examined with respective controls after required time intervals. For each compound the lowest concentration that is able to completely prevent the growth of microorganisms was determined and represented as minimal inhibitory concentration (MIC in mg/ml) of the compound. The compound having the lowest MIC values would have the highest antimicrobial activity against the pathogen.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The analytical data (Table 1) of the complexes (1-5) suggest the formula of the macrocyclic complexes as: $[M(C_{10}H_{20}N_4)_2].X^-$, where $M = La^{3+}, Ce^{3+}, Nd^{3+}, Sm^{3+}$ and Eu^{3+} and $X = NO_3^-$ and Cl^- . All the complexes are sparingly soluble in common organic solvents such as ethanol and methanol but highly soluble in DMF and DMSO. Molar conductance values of all the complexes in DMF (Table 1) fall in the expected range of 1:1 electrolytes. All complexes give satisfactory elemental analyses results, as shown in Table 1 and fit well the following structure:

Fig.1 Proposed Structure of complexes with L.
Where $M = La^{3+}, Ce^{3+}, Nd^{3+}, Sm^{3+}$ and Eu^{3+} and $X = NO_3^-$ and Cl^-

Magnetic measurements and electronic spectra

The observed magnetic moment values for $Ce^{3+}, Nd^{3+}, Sm^{3+}$ and Eu^{3+} complexes suggest their octahedral

geometry [16] around the metal ion. Which is being further confirmed by the appearance of two bands in its electronic spectrum at 15850 cm^{-1} and 19982 cm^{-1} , reasonably be assigned to ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g}$ and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g}$

transitions, respectively.. The Electronic spectra of the complexes are dominated by an intense single band in the range $32463\text{-}37665\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to charge transfer transition.

Table 1: Analytical, physical and spectral data of the complexes (1-5) derived from [Me₂(12)dieneN₄]

Complex/Colour	M.Pt. (^o C)	Yield%	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	Analysis%:Found (Calcd.)						UV-Vis Spectra λ_{max} (cm^{-1})
				C	H	N	O	Cl	M	
[La(C ₁₀ H ₂₀ N ₄).Cl ₂].Cl ⁻ Light brown	317	65	0	36.5 (36.8)	6.1 (6.2)	17.3 (17.2)	-	21.6 (21.7)	18.3 (18.1)	15846, 19986, 32459
[Ce(C ₁₀ H ₂₀ N ₄)(NO ₃) ₂].NO ₃ ⁻ Green	289	76	3.46	30.8 (31.7)	5.1 (5.3)	21.9 (22.1)	-	-	15.9 (15.5)	13012, 15906, 33312
[Nd(C ₁₀ H ₂₀ N ₄)(NO ₃) ₂].NO ₃ ⁻ Light brown	315	62	2.29	30.6 (31.3)	4.9 (5.3)	22.0 (21.9)	25.0 (25.3)	-	16.2 (16.6)	15486, 26418, 36342
[Sm(C ₁₀ H ₂₀ N ₄)Cl ₂] ⁺ .Cl ⁻ Light brown	305	58	1.49	33.6 (33.9)	5.3 (5.7)	15.2 (15.8)	25.4 (25.0)	29.4 (29.9)	15.0 (14.7)	15616, 37404
[Eu(C ₁₀ H ₂₀ N ₄)Cl ₂] ⁺ .Cl ⁻ Brown	324	67	3.54	33.9 (33.5)	5.8 (5.6)	15.1 (15.6)	-	29.2 (29.7)	15.9 (15.6)	15826, 37672

Table 2: Infrared spectral data of the complexes (1-5) derived from [Me₂(12)dieneN₄]

Complex	C=N (cm-1)	NH (cm-1)	M-N (cm-1)
[La(C ₁₀ H ₂₀ N ₄).Cl ₂].Cl ⁻	1632	3238	466
[Ce(C ₁₀ H ₂₀ N ₄)(NO ₃) ₂].NO ₃ ⁻	1646	3246	422
[Nd(C ₁₀ H ₂₀ N ₄)(NO ₃) ₂].NO ₃ ⁻	1644	3240	426
[Sm(C ₁₀ H ₂₀ N ₄)Cl ₂] ⁺ .Cl ⁻	1638	3258	452
[Eu(C ₁₀ H ₂₀ N ₄)Cl ₂] ⁺ .Cl ⁻	1648	3254	438

IR Spectra

The IR spectra of all the complexes (Table 2) show a single sharp band in the region $3240\text{-}3260\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to N-H stretching vibrations of secondary amines [14] moiety. The appearance of a strong absorption band in the region $1630\text{-}1650\text{ cm}^{-1}$ corresponds to C=N

stretching frequency [15]. No band is observed around $1700\text{-}1800\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating the condensation of amine and the ketone. A band appearing at $421\text{-}494\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region can be ascribed [16] to $\nu(\text{M-N})$ vibrations which further confirms the coordination of these groups with the metal ion. The band corresponding to $\nu(\text{M-N})$ in

the range 421–492 cm⁻¹ [16]. The appearance of various IR bands in the nitrate complexes clearly reveals the presence of coordinated and uncoordinated NO₃ ions.

¹H NMR

The ¹H NMR spectrum of macrocyclic La (III) complex in DMSO-d₆ shows a broad singlet at δ1.64-1.84 attributable to the imine methyl (CH₃-C=N, 6H) protons. Two multiplets in the region 3.12-3.38 and 2.28-2.38 ppm may be due to the non equivalent methylene protons (C-CH₂-N=, 4H) and (C-CH₂-N, 8H) of the amine moiety. A multiplet in the region 8.02-8.06 ppm corresponds to the secondary amino protons (C-NH-C, 2H).

Antimicrobial Screening

In this study, all the chemically synthesized metal complexes were screened for antimicrobial activity

against bacterial and fungal strains. The minimum inhibitory concentrations (MIC) values of these synthetic complexes were determined by Serial dilution method. All the metal complexes show significant antibacterial activity against some pathogens (Table 3). Complexes 1 and 5 exhibited good activities against all the tested bacterial strains except II and VII ranging from 0.088 to 0.202 mg/ml. Complex 5 showed the highest inhibition (0.088 and 0.099 mg/ml) against Klebsiella pneumonia MTCC 2405 & Pseudomonas aeruginosa MTCC 2295 (Table 3). Based on the MIC values shown by these complexes against bacteria, Europium and lanthanum complexes were found to be the most effective. The antifungal activities of all the complexes were determined against three fungal strains, i.e., Aspergillus niger and Aspergillus flavus and Candida tropicalis. In the whole series, complex 3 showed the highest percentage inhibition against all the fungal strains, but none of the tested complexes restricted the fungal growth excellently.

Table 3: Results of Antimicrobial activity of the metal complexes of [Me₂(12)dieneN₄]

Complex	Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) in mg/ml against									
	Bacteria							Fungi		
	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X
[La(C ₁₀ H ₂₀ N ₄)Cl ₂].Cl ⁻	0.088	-	0.098	0.98	0.090	0.102	-	0.088	0.080	0.092
[Ce(C ₁₀ H ₂₀ N ₄)(NO ₃) ₂].NO ₃ ⁻	0.102	-	0.202	0.180	0.085	0.173	-	0.128	0.096	0.098
[Nd(C ₁₀ H ₂₀ N ₄)(NO ₃) ₂].NO ₃ ⁻	0.104	-	0.109	0.99	0.112	0.108	-	0.062	0.052	0.058
[Sm(C ₁₀ H ₂₀ N ₄)Cl ₂] ⁺ .Cl ⁻	0.102	-	0.112	0.110	0.102	0.120	-	0.075	0.095	0.085
[Eu(C ₁₀ H ₂₀ N ₄)Cl ₂] ⁺ .Cl ⁻	0.098	-	0.088	0.099	0.098	0.095	-	0.082	0.090	0.099

CONCLUSION

Based on elemental analyses, magnetic measurements, electronic, IR and NMR spectral studies, the structure as shown in Fig. 1 may be proposed for all the prepared complexes. Antimicrobial activity of complexes shows that the macrocyclic complexes are very effective on tested microorganisms. It has been suggested that chelation/coordination reduces the polarity of the metal ion mainly because of the partial sharing of its positive charge with the donor group within the whole chelate ring system. This process of

chelation thus increases the lipophilic nature of the central metal atom, which in turn, favors its permeation through the lipid layer of membranes, thus causing the metal complex to cross the bacterial membrane more effectively thus increasing the activity of the complexes [17]. In addition to this, many other factors such as solubility, dipole moment influenced by the metal ion may be the possible reasons for the antibacterial activities of these metal complexes.

REFERENCES

1. K. Bernot, K.C Daiguebonne, G Calvez, Y Suffren, O Guillou. A journey in lanthanide coordination chemistry: from evaporable dimers to magnetic materials and luminescent devices, *Acc Chem Res*, 54 (2) (2021), p. 427.
2. A Zabala-Lekuona, JM Seco, E Colacio. Single-molecule magnets: from Mn12-ac to dysprosium metallocenes, a travel in time, *Coord Chem Rev* (2021), p. 441
3. H Pellissier. Recent developments in enantioselective lanthanide-catalyzed transformations, *Coord Chem Rev*, 336 (2017), p. 96
4. Mortensen KT, Osberger TJ, King, TA, Sore H, Spring, DR. Strategies for the Diversity-Oriented Synthesis of Macrocycles, *Chem. Rev.* 119(2019),10288–10317. DOI: [10.1021/acs.chemrev.9b00084](https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemrev.9b00084)
5. Singh A K, Singh R, Baniwal S. Kinetics of acid promoted dissociation reactions of Cu [Ph₄(14) tetraene N₄] macrocyclic complex, *IJCA*, 41A (March 2002), 537-540.
6. Liu Y, Zhao Z, Huo R, Liu Q. Two macrocycle-based sensors for anions sensing, *Sci Rep*, 9(2019), 502.
7. Baniwal S, Chandra S, Singh AK. Poly (vinyl chloride)-based macrocyclic membrane sensors for magnesium, *Talanta*, 50 (1999), 499-508.
8. Delgado R, Costa J, K P. Guerra, Lima LM. Lanthanide complexes of macrocyclic derivatives useful for medical applications. *Pure Appl. Chem.*, Vol. 77, No. 3, pp. 569–579, 2005. <https://doi.org/10.1351/pac200577030569>
9. Mallinson J, Collins I. Macrocycles in new drug discovery, *Future Med. Chem.*, 4(11) (2012), 1409-1438.
10. Yao J, Dou W, Liu W, Zheng J (2009). Synthesis, crystal structures and photoluminescent properties of the complexes of a new coumarin derivative with lanthanide ions. *Inorg Chem Commun*, 12(5), 430-432.
11. Rahman I M, Begum Z A, Hasegawa H (2013). Selective separation of elements from complex solution matrix with molecular recognition plus macrocycles attached to a solid-phase: A review. *Microchem J*, 110, 485-493.
12. Gerald C F, Zhang S, Sherry AD (2004). Comparison of crystal field dependent and independent methods to analyse lanthanide induced NMR shifts in axially symmetric complexes. Part I. Systems with a C₃ symmetry axis. *Inorganica chim acta*, 357(2), 381-395.
13. Rios JL, Recio MC, Villar A. Screening methods for natural products with antimicrobial activity: A review of the literature. *J. Ethnopharm*, 23 (1988), 127.
14. Shiekh R A, Rahman IA, Malik, MA, Luddin N, Masudi SM, Al-Thabaiti SA. Transition metal complexes with mix-nitrogen-sulphur (N-S) donor macrocyclic Schiff base ligand: Synthesis, spectral, electrochemical and antimicrobial studies, *Int J Electrochem Sci*, 8 (2013), 6972-6987.
15. Holtzman MS, Cummings SC. Macrocyclic nickel (II) complexes with new dimethyl-substituted 13- and 14-membered tetraaza ligands. *Inorg Chem*, 15, (1976) 660.
16. Shakir M, Varkey SP, Hameed PS. Synthesis and characterization of Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) complexes of dithiadiazza macrocycles, *J Chem Res*, 11 (1993), 442.
17. Chohan ZH, Pervez H, Rauf A, Khan KM, Supuran CT. Isatin-derived antibacterial and antifungal compounds and their transition metal complexes. *J Enzyme Inhib Med Chem* 2004, 19:417–23.